

Research

Incidence and Pattern of Mandibular Fractures in Janakpur, Madhesh Pradesh, Nepal : A Retrospective Study

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Abstract: Objective: To summarize and discuss the significance of various aetiological factors in determining the incidence and dictating the patterns of mandibular fractures in Janakpur, Nepal. The patients age, sex composition, etiology and distribution were analyzed.

Methods: 152 patients treated for mandibular fractures were reviewed between the time periods from June 2015 to May 2019 in dental department of Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal. Data on age, gender, aetiology, use of intoxicants, head injury, associated injuries, days of the week, anatomic site and multiple fractures within the mandible were recorded and assessed. SPSS 15.0 software was used for statistical analysis. The comparison between data was performed. $P < 0.05$ indicated that the difference was statistically significant.

Results: The highest incidence of fractures was observed among the individuals in 21-30yrs (3rd decade) (33.55%) followed by 2nd(11-20yrs) and 4thdecades(31-40yrs), which exhibited 40 and 30 cases (26.3% and 19.7%), respectively. Male to female ratio was biased (4:1) portraying a male predominance. Road traffic accidents (RTAs) were observed to be the predominant aetiological factor responsible accounting for 79.2% of the total injuries followed by assaults (11.8%) and falls (9%). Parasymphysis exhibited the highest incidence (32.63%) amongst the anatomic sites, followed by body (18.75%), angle (16.66%), condyle (15.27%), symphysis (12.50%), ramus (2.77%) and coronoid (1.38%).

Conclusion: Mandibular fractures occur most likely in young and middle-aged males in Madhesh province, Janakpur, Nepal. A definitive relationship existed between RTA and the incidence of mandibular fractures. The frequency further increased with consumption of social intoxicants. The most commonly fractured site was parasymphysis either isolated or associated with other fractures in the mandible.

Keywords: mandibular fracture; RTA; complication; injuries

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Introduction

Mandible is the only active bone of the human maxillofacial region, at the front and lower position of the facial and is horseshoe shape. Although the texture of the mandible is firm, it also has weak anatomical position which can easily lead to fracture by improper external force[1]. Mandibular bone has a unique anatomical structure and physiological characteristics, the location of fracture is related with its stress position and the fracture can cause occlusion disorders, chewing dysfunction and other complications which make the mandibular fracture more specially[2]. Many countries have made different research and analysis on mandibular fracture, however the studies in different regions and times

made the different results. The influence factors such as culture, economy, social status and even religion can affect the incidence of mandibular fracture[3]. At present, there was no relative search on the distribution of mandibular fractures which was divided by the age, sex composition and etiology in Janakpur, Nepal. The maxillofacial area is one of the most important anatomical parts of the human body, and it is closely related to the surrounding tissues. Injuries to the maxillofacial area will cause complications in the surrounding important anatomical organs such as the brain and eyeballs, as well as fractures, affecting the shape and appearance of the face. Beautiful, when it affects the respiratory tract, it may even endanger the life of the patient[4-6]. Maxillofacial fractures are one of the common traumas in the maxillofacial region. Compared with traumas in other parts of the body, the maxillofacial region does not have rich soft tissue coverage[7,8]. When it is subjected to external violent impact, it is often unable to get a good buffer, so the incidence of fractures is relatively slightly high. The mandible is the most prominent part of the maxillofacial region, so it is one of the most common sites for maxillofacial fractures, just like the high points of the cheekbones and nasal bones [9,10]. The particularity of the mandible lies not only in its prominent position in the maxillofacial region, but also in its function. As the only movable bone in the maxillofacial region, the mandible is responsible for many functions such as language, chewing, occlusion, and facial appearance. The inferior alveolar nerve and the facial nerve are also important nerves involved in the mandible[11]. When the fracture affects these nerves, it will cause the patient's maxillofacial sensory and motor abnormalities, and in severe cases, it may even cause secondary psychological trauma to the patient[9], especially the presence of teeth, the treatment of mandibular fractures requires a more complex oral environment, more surgical restrictions, and a more unstable postoperative state[12]. The location of the fracture is related to the location and direction of the external force. Due to its prominent position, it is more susceptible to fractures induced by violent factors from all directions. Moreover, although the mandible is relatively tough in general, there are several relatively weak anatomical structures, such as the median symphysis, mental foramen, mandibular angle, and condyle, etc., so these parts become prone to mandibular fractures. At present, there have been many reports on mandibular fractures. Bo Bin et al. [13] found that mandibular fractures accounted for as high as 59.34% of maxillofacial fractures. The incidence characteristics of different regions and different groups of people are different, and the factors that affect these results are also various, such as the local education and economic level, the social background of the people studied, and even differences in religion will also lead to differences in the survey results[14,15]. Therefore, at a certain level, understanding the epidemiological characteristics of mandibular fractures in a region or country is helpful to assess the behavior patterns and characteristics of populations in different regions and countries, and provide guidance information for the local prevention and treatment of the disease.

Research Methodology

The present retrospective study included data collected from total number of 152 male and female patients who had reported to the casualty of Janaki Medical College and teaching hospital in the time period from June 2015 to May 2019. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee. All patients were in the 1st(1-10yrs) to 6th(51-60yrs) decade of life and having associated/concomitant facial and other skeletal bone fractures were included in the study except patients whose records were found incomplete, patients with severe systemic and multi-organ injuries, financial constraints of the patient, patients who required tertiary centre referral for further management of multi-organ injuries, patients who succumbed to the injuries, and who left against medical advice were excluded. Simple descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 15.0 software (SPSS).

Results

Out of the total sample of 152 patients, 126 (82.9%) were males and 26 (17.1%) were females pointing out to a male preponderance (5.5:1). Majority (33.55%) were in the age group of 21–30 years followed by 11–20 years (26.3%). This shows that the young adults are mostly affected (Table 1). The RTAs (79.2%) clearly predominated in both genders, being the single largest reported etiological factor contributing to the majority of mandibular fractures followed by assaults (11.8%) and falls (9%) (Table 2). A total of 51 cases (35.4%) out of the study population reported the use of intoxicants. A majority used alcohol (58.9%) followed by toddy [local brew from date palms/sugarcanes] (33.3%) and 7.8% of patients used Ganja or Opioids (Table 3). With regard to the frequency of distribution of injuries by the day of the week, Sunday appeared to be the day on which maximum injuries were sustained (30.55%) (Table 4). Our findings reveal that 50.6% of the patients (73 cases out of 144) with mandibular fractures had associated injuries, out of which

head injury accounted for the greater majority of the associated injuries (21.6%) (Table 5). Based on the anatomical site, parasymphysis fractures (32.63%) were most common followed by body (18.75%), angle (16.66%) and condyle (15.27%) (Table 6). Amongst combination fractures (2 fractures), the most prevalent were parasymphysis with angle constituting 6 out of 144 (4.16%). This was followed by symphysis with condyle in 5 cases (3.47%), parasymphysis with condyle in 4 cases (2.77%), parasymphysis with body in 3 cases (2.08%), angle with condyle in 2 cases (1.38%), followed by bilateral parasymphysis in 5 cases (3.47%), bilateral angle in 3 cases (2.08%), bilateral condyle in 2 cases (1.38%), and even in multiple fractures sites (more than two fractures in the mandible) parasymphysis was the most commonly involved site.

Table 1 – Distribution of the sample according to age and gender.

Age(years)	Male(%)	Female(%)	Total(%)
1-10	12(9.5)	2(7.7)	14(9.7)
11-20	31(24.6)	9(34.6)	40(26.3)
21-30	43(34.12)	8(30.7)	51(33.55)
31-40	26(20.6)	4(15.38)	30(19.7)
41-50	7(5.5)	2(7.69)	9(5.9)
51-60	7(5.5)	1(3.85)	8(5.26)
Total	126(82.9)	26(17.1)	152(100)

Table 2 – Comparison of aetiology for trauma according to gender.

Aetiology of trauma	Males(%)	Females(%)	Total(%)
Road traffic accidents(RTA)	100(87.7)	14(12.3)	114(79.2)
Falls/fall from height	8(61.5)	5(38.5)	13(9)
Assaults	14(82.4)	3(17.6)	17(11.8)

Table 3 – Use of various intoxicants in the study population.

Type of intoxicant	Males(%)	Females(%)	Total(%)
Alcohol	30(60)	0(0)	30(58.9)
Opioids/Ganja	4(8)	0(0)	4(7.8)
Rum	16(32)	1(100)	17(33.3)
Total	50(98)	1(2)	51(100)

Table 4 – Associated injuries reported in the study population.

Type of injuries	Number	Percentage
Head injury	31	21.6
Le Fort III	4	2.77
NOE fracture	1	0.69
Le Fort II	10	6.94
Le Fort I	3	2.08

ZMC	6	4.16
Cervical injury	1	0.69
Clavicle	9	6.24
Rib	2	1.38
Radius	2	1.38
Femur	3	2.08
Fibula	1	0.69
Total	63	48.67

Table 6 – Distribution of fractures based on anatomic site.

Types of fracture	Number of cases	Percentage	Isolated cases	Associated with other fracture in mandible	Bilateral (same anatomical location on the contralateral side)
Parasymphysis	47	32.63	24	18	5
Body	27	18.75	22	5	0
Angle	24	16.66	8	13	3
Condyle	22	15.27	2	18	2
Symphysis	18	12.50	10	8	0
Ramus	4	2.77	4	0	0
Coronoid	2	1.38	1	1	0

Amongst combination fractures (2 fractures), the most prevalent were parasymphysis with angle constituting 6 out of 152 (3.95%). This was followed by symphysis with condyle in 5 cases (3.47%), parasymphysis with condyle in 4 cases (2.77%), parasymphysis with body in 3 cases (2.08%), angle with condyle in 2 cases (1.38%), followed by bilateral parasymphysis in 5 cases (3.47%), bilateral angle in 3 cases (2.08%), bilateral condyle in 2 cases (1.38%), and even in multiple fractures sites (more than two fractures in the mandible) parasymphysis was the most commonly involved site.

Discussion

In our study population, 51 out of 152 (33.55%) patients were under the influence of one amongst the many intoxicants prevalent. The majority, i.e. 30 out of 51 cases (58.9%), were under the influence of alcohol, while 17 cases (33.3%) were under the influence alcohol based beverage obtained from date palm/sugarcane trees. A small proportion of patients (7.8%) used Ganja or Opioids due to widely prevalent illegal cultivation of poppy plants. Most of the practices were observed in males (98%). This is in accordance with Oikarinen et al.,[16] which accounts about 44%, whereas the study conducted in Nigeria, alcohol was associated with only about 20% of jaw fractures, a proportion significantly lower than reported elsewhere.[17]

It is the common experience of the surgeons training maxillofacial injuries that a high proportion of our patients are under the influence of alcohol/intoxicants at the time of admission into the hospital. Such patients are seldom fully conscious at the time of presentation and might even be unconscious. Being under the influence of alcohol at the time of presentation their sensory responses may not be sharp and poor Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores might influence the GCS scores on casual examination. Especially influenced is the recollection of events immediately around the events that led to the trauma. Another undesirable outcome of heavy drinking might be vomitus complicating the airway

management. It is frequently due to gastritis as a direct effect of alcohol on gastric mucosal lining and might be a confounding factor for the vomitus influenced by triggering of Chemotactic Trigger Zone (CTZ) on alteration of intracranial pressure upon head injury which is of high significance in case of primary assessment of the extent of head injury. Impaired motor coordination as a direct consequence of alcoholism leading to RTA has been substantiated by numerous studies on the subject revealing statistically significant correlation between the incidence of Maxillofacial Trauma and alcoholism.[18]

Head injury was observed in 21.6% in our total patients. There is a high incidence of head and cervical spine injuries associated with maxillofacial trauma in RTA victims. This is due to the fact that when a forward moving vehicle is brought to an abrupt halt, the unrestrained occupants will be thrown upwards and forwards until their movement is arrested by some part of the vehicle, or if they are forcefully ejected from the vehicle on contact with the ground or other objects. The head may come in contact with the windscreen or the roof of the vehicle and thus absorb maximum energy of the impact.

According to Khan et al.[19] in 2011, the most commonly involved site of mandibular fracture in patients with and without head injury was parasymphysis followed by condyle. This is in accordance with our study. In contrast to this, Hung et al.[19] showed that the body/angle is the region with the highest rate of fractures. Czerwinski et al.[20] revealed that in the positive head injury group, the majority of patients (54.5%) sustained single mandibular fracture while in the negative head injury group, the majority of patients (51.6%) sustained double fractures. It has been hypothesized that when the mandible sustains fewer fractures, the dissipation of energy is reduced and more force is transmitted to the cranial vault, thereby resulting in a higher incidence of loss of consciousness. Multiple fracture patterns likely serve as a neuroprotective mechanism, allowing greater dissipation of forces and resulting in less residual energy to be transmitted to the cranial vault.

Our findings reveal that 63 out of 152 cases (41.4%) with mandibular fractures had associated injuries. Head injury accounted for the greater majority of associated injuries (21.6%). The incidence of head injury in this study may have been influenced by the non-enforcement of seat belt and motorcycle helmet legislations in Janakpur, Nepal. This was followed by 10 cases of Le Fort II (6.94%), clavicle (6.24%), Zygomatico Maxillary Complex (4.16%), Le Fort III (2.77%) and Femur and Le Fort I (2.08% each). Varying frequency of associated injuries in Maxillofacial trauma reported by Ugboke et al.[17] was 81.3%, Adakeye[21] 46.7%, Obeukwe and Etetafia[22] 44.2%, Rocca et al.[11] 23.2%, Oji[23] 23% and by Down et al.[24] was 16%.

In this study, the occurrence of injuries when compared to the other days of the week, Sunday (30.55%) was found to be most common day followed by Saturday (25%). Remaining 64 cases (44.4%) reported between Monday and Friday. Weekends appear to be the days on which maximum injuries were sustained, which could be attributed to a plethora of causative factors such as increased frequency of travel due to social reasons and higher probability of intoxication due to leisure activities on event of a holiday, have reported Friday as the day of the week with maximum prevalence of maxillofacial trauma, have reported that Saturday and Sunday were the days of the week with the reported maximum number of maxillofacial trauma. Our results are consistent with the findings of the later authors.

The most common sites of fracture in the mandible in this study in descending order were parasymphysis 47 (32.63%), body 27 (18.75%), angle 24 (16.66%) and condyle 22 (15.27%). The results of Vyas et al.[12], and Ajmal et al.[27] were similar to the results of our study. In contrary to our study, the other commonest sites involved in mandible as reported by other authors are symphysis,[28,29] mandibular body,[30-33] angle,[34,35] and condyle.[36,37] The difference might be a reflection of the causative factors.

In our study, we observed that out of 152 mandibular fractures, single fracture (isolated fractures) in mandible was reported (49.30%). Amongst combination fractures (2 fractures in the mandible), we observed that parasymphysis was commonly associated with angle (6 cases), which is in accordance with the report by Dongus and Hall,[34] and in contrary to our study, Ogundare et al.[35] have reported that body with angle as the most common combination. Next most common combinations were symphysis and condyle (5 cases) followed by parasymphysis and condyle (4 cases), parasymphysis and body (3 cases), angle and condyle (2 cases). Among multiple fractures (more than two fractures in the mandible) were reported in 6 cases[36,37].

Conclusion

The mandibular fractures occur in people of all ages, RTA being the chief cause of such injuries. The highest incidence of mandibular fractures was observed in 2nd(11-20yrs) and 3rd(21-30yrs) decade of life and that the parasymphysis was

the most commonly involved site. Maxillofacial trauma may coexist with other injuries and conversely injuries elsewhere may exist in patients with maxillofacial trauma. So it is necessary for the maxillofacial surgeon to be a part of multidisciplinary trauma team. Furthermore, the results of this data will be helpful for the government agencies and health care professionals towards planning future programs on prevention.

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